

CCG POLICY BRIEF

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy Systems Modelling: Utility-scale Battery Systems

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Summary

Renewable technologies such as solar PV and onshore wind are expected to play a substantial role in the global energy transition, offering low-cost, scalable sources of electricity that will likely supply a substantial portion of future energy demand. However, these variable sources of renewable electricity need to be paired with back-up generation and/or grid-scale storage to maintain a secure, reliable supply of low-carbon electricity to the grid. Battery energy storage systems (BESSs) are the fastest growing form of power system flexibility and will be critical to integrating large shares of variable renewable energy onto the grid.

The evaluation of suitable grid-scale storage technologies relies on technical insights gained from energy or power system modelling (ESM). However, these insights are very sensitive to assumptions over the capital and operating costs of storage technologies. In countries with limited or no experience with deploying of grid-scale storage, there are substantial challenges in selecting accurate cost assumptions, which could impair the usefulness of their insights. Here, we discuss how global ranges taken from the open literature could be used to define and justify assumptions for utility-scale batteries.

Key Policy Recommendations

- The sensitivity of energy system modelling (ESM) to the costs of BESSs needs to be accounted for when used to provide technical insights for policy frameworks and/or Nationally Determined Contributions.
- Academic researchers, government ministries, and other stakeholders operating in countries which lack empirical data on the costs of deploying BESSs need to clearly present and justify cost assumptions used for ESMs.
- Global cost ranges from the open literature can be a useful tool to situate cost assumptions for ESMs but are not a substitute for direct engagement with local developers and industry stakeholders.

Economic Data Gaps & Challenges for Energy System Modelling of Utility-Scale Battery Energy Storage

Introduction

Utility-scale Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESSs) are some of the most scalable, low-cost forms of grid-scale energy storage. They will play an important role in facilitating the scale-up of variable renewable electricity sources, such as onshore wind and solar PV, globally and addressing issues with intermittency. The International Energy Agency predicts in its Announced Pledges Scenario that the installed capacity globally could increase more than 16 to 725 GW in 2030 from an existing 45 GW in 2022 [1]. With widespread deployment, the impact of a high penetration of variable renewable sources could be addressed through the use of utility-scale BESSs to provide balancing services on a minute, hourly, and daily basis.

The costs of BESSs have fallen dramatically in the past decade due to the rapid scale-up of technologies such as lithium-ion batteries for demands ranging from consumer devices to electric vehicles and grid-scale BESSs. Nonetheless, there is still substantial uncertainty over the future costs of grid-scale BESSs. Pressure on existing supply chains and demand for critical minerals are driving the uncertainty in future costs, with the International Renewable Energy Agency predicting in their Electricity Storage and Renewables Report in 2017 that the cost of lithium-ion cell technologies vary between 473 to 1,260 USD/kWh, a ratio of over 3x (storage costs can be measured both on power output and total storage basis, with a specified ratio between the two for different technologies and configurations) [2].

Existing research has recognised the issues with data scarcity for utility-scale electricity storage [3] and the importance of cost reductions to support the scale-up of BESSs [4]. However, there is little discussion of how the total costs of deployment may vary between different countries and geographic regions, with some global studies adopting uniform costs for BESSs [5]. This policy brief outlines a curated dataset that presents global ranges of the technoeconomic parameters (i.e. capital costs, operating costs) which are key to modelling the costs of BESSs, drawn from the open and grey literature. The aim of this brief is to discuss the challenges around data availability for BESSs, especially in the Global South, whilst providing energy system modellers and other stakeholders with a method of situating and justifying their cost assumptions for energy system models (ESMs) in the absence of empirical data.

Drawing upon the existing literature base

Technoeconomic data on utility-scale BESSs were gathered to inform the assumptions used in large-scale energy system modelling tools such as the OSeMOSYS open-source model. [6]. Relevant data were collected from websites, reports, academic articles, and databases of national and international organisations. The data covers the range of parameters needed for the technoeconomic analysis of utility-scale BESSs, including operating costs, capital costs, construction times and total operational lifetime. The dataset has been made openly accessible in the Zenodo Data Repository and can be accessed via the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10890349>. The dataset shared on the Zenodo link contains the sources that were used to populate the database.

Global current capital costs for BESSs

Error! Reference source not found. shows the range of overnight capital costs and fixed operating costs for the deployment of BESSs, taken across 2020–2024 and categorised into lithium-ion and vanadium redox-flow battery systems. The capital costs extracted from the open and grey literature between 2020–2024 show substantial variation, with a median value of 402 USD/kWh for all battery types (which includes some batteries sub-types not including in Figure 1). Data that were found in the open literature were predominantly from the USA, with substantial data gaps for the rest of the world due to limited empirical data from project deployment.

Figure 1: Range of a) capital costs and b) fixed operating costs relative to capacity in 2020–2024 for lithium-ion and vanadium redox-flow BESSs. Costs are measured relative to total storage capacity in USD/kWh and stated in 2023 US dollar terms, but the [Zenodo database](#) also contains costs measured relative to power output and with details of the storage duration. There were no data available on fixed operating costs for vanadium redox-flow batteries between 2020–2024. The lower and upper bounds of each shaded box represent the lower and upper quartile of the data (25th and 75th percentile respectively), with the central line representing the median. Whiskers represent the range of values falling within 1.5 times the inter-quartile range. The 25th, 50th, and 75th percentile values are written to the left of each bar.

Using global ranges to address empirical data gaps

Utility-scale BESSs will play an important role globally in supporting the transition to a clean energy system, though in many countries and regions there has been limited deployment (including much of the Global South). The International Energy Agency estimates in its Net Zero Emissions by 2050 Scenario that grid-scale BESSs needs to increase nearly 100x to 4,199 GW by 2050 from the current level of 45 GW in 2022 to support the rapid upscaling of variable renewables like solar and wind energy [1].

Understanding the current and future costs of deployment will be key to the effective design of policy support and the development of appropriate integrated energy and climate strategies. **Figure 2** shows the range of capital costs between 2020–2024 by region (where available) and projected global costs in 2030 and 2050 for lithium-ion, which is expected to be the dominant technology for BESSs. There is only data available for North America, as demonstrated by Figure 2 highlighting the data availability gaps for parameters such as installation or financing costs that are key to the effective understanding of the costs of deploying utility-scale BESSs. These data gaps create significant difficulties for energy system modellers around the selection and justification of cost assumptions for utility-scale BESSs.

Figure 2: Range of capital costs for lithium-ion batteries in a) 2020–2024 , where available, and b) global projections for 2030 and 2050. Costs are measured relative to total storage capacity in USD/kWh, but the Zenodo database also contains costs measured relative to power output and with details of the storage duration. Costs are stated in 2023 US dollar terms.

In countries and regions with limited deployment of utility-scale BESSs, it is important for energy system modellers to clearly highlight the cost assumptions used in power and energy system modelling, as the decarbonisation pathways and technical insights developed from modelling may be highly sensitive to the costs of BESSs. Transparent documentation of assumptions and methodologies will also increase confidence in the modelling results, facilitating informed decision-making by policymakers and other stakeholders. The ranges presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** are intended to serve as a useful tool to situate assumptions in ESMs for these countries against empirical data taken from other countries and regions, addressing the data gaps whilst still providing robust technical insights to support the development of energy and climate strategies by policymakers.

Prioritising transparency and data sharing amongst stakeholders will also be essential to enhance the accuracy and utility of ESMs. By openly sharing data and methodologies, academic researchers, government ministries, industry professionals, and other stakeholders can work collaboratively to address data gaps, compare and contrast their assumptions, and so improve the reliability of energy system modelling outcomes. Given the potential sensitivity of ESMs to the costs of utility-scale BESSs, energy system modellers should also conduct sensitivity tests to assess the robustness of their models. Understanding how variations in cost assumptions impact model outcomes will be crucial for making informed decisions and developing resilient energy transition pathways, and situating their assumptions against the global cost curve could be a useful way of exploring model sensitivities.

However, whilst the global ranges from the open literature presented in this work can provide valuable insights and offer a way to address empirical data gaps, they should complement, not replace, direct engagement with private sector stakeholders. Collaborating with industry partners can enrich data collection efforts and ensure that ESMs accurately reflect real-world conditions and the true costs of utility-scale BESSs.

Conclusions

Addressing the challenges of data availability for utility-scale BESSs will be critical to accelerating the energy transition, particularly in countries in the Global South where there is limited experience with the deployment of utility-scale BESSs. There is a need to recognise the sensitivity of ESMs to assumptions regarding the costs of utility-scale BESSs, as well as to prioritise transparency and data sharing and to justify cost assumptions in regions with limited empirical data. In so doing, energy system modellers and other stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and reliability of the scenarios generated from ESMs, to ensure their accuracy and relevance to policy. Whilst global ranges from the open and grey literature can serve as useful reference points, engaging with public and private sector stakeholders will be essential for understanding and capturing the complexities of real-world deployment scenarios.

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